

Detection of Plastic Waste in Various Water Bodies Using Remote Sensing Data

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1 Introduction

Figure 1. A large amount of debris accumulated near the Visegrad Dam after it broke, 2021

Figure 2. Plastic from Guatemala's Motagua River pollutes Roatan's beaches, 2017

Plastic pollution in aquatic environments is a major global issue.

Every year, tons of waste enter rivers, lakes, and oceans from urban runoff, industrial discharge, tourism, and poorly managed landfills. Debris such as bottles, bags, and packaging accumulates on shorelines and water surfaces, disrupting ecosystems, harming wildlife, and degrading habitats.

Despite international awareness, plastic production keeps rising, especially in regions with weak environmental regulations. Many affected areas lack monitoring systems, making it difficult to track and reduce pollution. In some places (Fig. 1), problems with infrastructure can make waste accumulate quickly. In other regions (Fig. 2), lack of monitoring lets pollution travel far before being noticed.

This thesis aims to design and evaluate a processing pipeline for detecting floating plastic debris in aquatic environments using multispectral satellite imagery and integrates two complementary components:

- **Debris segmentation** – a deep-learning object detection model applied to satellite images to identify and delineate floating debris.
- **Spectral classification** – a supervised model using spectral indices to classify pixels by material type and estimate the composition of detected debris.

3 Methodology

Figure 5. General debris detection and classification pipeline

The pipeline (Fig. 5) uses a segmentation mask to filter candidate pixels for subsequent classification.

Segmentation dataset & evaluation

Floating debris was annotated as a single class **debris** in **Roboflow**, and training tiles were generated from the TCI product. Segmentation performance was measured on the validation split using COCO-style metrics: mAP50, mAP50-95, and recall. Model selection followed a two-step process: first selecting the best hyperparameter configuration within each model size (nano, small, medium), then comparing top variants to choose the final model.

Classification dataset, training & formal evaluation

Suspected debris pixels were labeled manually in **QGIS** at selected validation sites. An SVM with an RBF kernel was trained in an intentionally overfitting manner to replicate class-wise spectral signatures from the labeled samples.

Because the feature space is only two-dimensional, model hyperparameters were tuned manually at an expert level, leveraging knowledge of the physical meaning of the indices to shape the model behavior. To verify that, a formal evaluation was performed on a hold-out test subset using a confusion matrix and derived metrics (accuracy, precision, recall, F1).

Evaluation on real-world scenes

An object-level assessment was conducted on additional validation scenes, combining classifier predictions, manual ground-truth annotations, and segmentation masks. A two-stage evaluation compared classifier-alone performance with segmentation-filtered predictions to measure the effect on false positives and background suppression.

5 Conclusions and Future Work

This work developed and validated a two-step pipeline for floating plastic detection using Sentinel-2 MSI imagery.

A *medium YOLOv11-seg model* trained on a relatively small (~750-tile) segmentation dataset, combined with a deliberately *overfitted SVM classifier*, was able to detect debris across diverse environments. While performance remains not perfect, the approach reliably reduced false positives and provided consistent material classification, even in challenging conditions such as mixed debris, turbid water, and partial cloud cover.

Practical outputs of this work include:

- Curated and annotated segmentation dataset of debris instances[2].
- Labeled classification dataset for spectral model development.
- Trained SVM classifier in NDVI-FDI feature space.
- Fine-tuned YOLOv11-seg model optimized for Sentinel-2 imagery.

Future work:

- Expand the segmentation dataset and apply context aware copy-paste augmentation.
- Automate training and hyperparameter search with RayTune to streamline model optimization.
- Extend the spectral feature space with selected Sentinel-2 bands and indices, guided by expert input, to address the current model's main limitation — false positives from water (plastic/pumice confusion) and clouds under challenging optical conditions.

2 Preliminaries

In this study, **Sentinel-2 MSI imagery** are used as the main data source. The bands used are listed in Table 1:

MSI Band	Descriptor	Wavelength (nm)	Resolution (m)
Band 4	Red	664.6	10
Band 6	Red Edge 2	740.5	20
Band 8	NIR	832.8	10
Band 11	SWIR1	1613.7	20

Also, **True Color Image (TCI) product** serves as the input for the instance segmentation task. Figures 3 and 4 show examples of debris from different sources but with similar filament-like shapes, supporting their treatment as a single class for segmentation.

Figure 3. Raft of pumice near Tonga, 2019

Figure 4. Suspected plastic debris, Honduras, Omoa, 2018

For classification, two spectral indices are derived from the selected bands:

- **Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI)**, commonly used to highlight vegetation
- **Floating Debris Index (FDI)**, introduced by Biermann[1], to separate floating materials from surrounding water.

Both indices are calculated from surface reflectance data (R_{rs}) which can be produced using either the **Sen2Cor** or **ACOLITE DSF** atmospheric correction methods. These two correction methods are compared to select the most suitable input before training the classification model.

$$NDVI = \frac{R_{rs,NIR} - R_{rs,RED}}{R_{rs,NIR} + R_{rs,RED}}$$
$$R'_{rs,NIR} = R_{rs,RE2} + (R_{rs,SWIR1} - R_{rs,RE2}) \times \left(\frac{\lambda_{NIR} - \lambda_{RED}}{\lambda_{SWIR1} - \lambda_{RED}} \right) \times 10$$
$$FDI = R_{rs,NIR} - R'_{rs,NIR}$$

For instance segmentation, the **Ultralytics implementation of YOLOv11** is used. For classification, a **Support Vector Machine (SVM)** serves as the chosen model.

4 Results

The *medium-sized segmentation model* was chosen as the best-performing variant during the selection process. While its test split performance (Table 2) is below the baseline mAP50-95 reported for general-purpose models (51.5 for Box and 41.5 for Mask), it still provides sufficiently accurate spatial priors to guide the classifier and narrow the search space for debris detection, despite the small training dataset (~750 images).

Box				Mask			
Precision	Recall	mAP50	mAP50-95	Precision	Recall	mAP50	mAP50-95
0.452	0.421	0.380	0.197	0.353	0.328	0.254	0.061

Table 2. Performance metrics of medium sized YOLOv11 instance segmentation model

Figure 6. SVM decision borders in NDVI - FDI feature space

While ACOLITE DSF improves separability for vegetative classes such as algae and seaweed, Sen2Cor preserves stronger separation between spectrally similar debris types like plastic and timber. Because plastic detection is a key objective, Sen2Cor was selected as the atmospheric correction method.

Next plot (Fig. 6) illustrates the resulting class separability in the given feature space: most classes are clearly distinguished, with only occasional overlap between pumice and water, and plastic and water, which represent the main sources of confusion in the classifier.

Real-world example

This example (Fig. 7) contains suspected algae and seaweed debris. Many non-debris pixels are mislabeled in the raw classification mainly as pumice (~62%) or plastic (~37%) reflecting the main areas of confusion between water and these debris classes. This produces very high recall (~0.99) but extremely low precision (~0.02). Applying the segmentation mask removes most false positives while retaining actual debris (algae, plastic, timber), improving precision to ~0.38 and maintaining recall at ~0.87, yielding a more balanced depiction of debris distribution.

Figure 7. Omoa Bay, Honduras, left to right: source image; segmentation detections; raw classification; classification adjusted by segmentation mask.

References:

- 1) Lauren Biermann, Daniel Clewley, Victor Martinez-Vicente and Konstantinos Topouzelis. Finding Plastic Patches in Coastal Waters using Optical Satellite Data. 2020
- 2) DebrisFilamentsSAM: Instance Segmentation Dataset. <https://universe.roboflow.com/carbrands-q509h/debrisfilamentssam/dataset/17>